

UNILATERAL RADIX ENTOMOLARIS IN PRIMARY FIRST MOLAR:- A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

A complete and thorough knowledge of primary teeth and their root canal anatomy is very essential for clinical success of the treatment. The presence of dental anomalies is lesser in primary teeth as compared to permanent dentition^{1,6}The overall morphology of primary teeth is completely different as compared to permanent in its enamel, dentin thickness and more accentuated pulp horns which lead to early spread of infection to the pulp as soon as the caries starts.^{1,2} The primary objective of pediatric endodontic therapy is thorough removal of the pulp tissue from all the roots and canals followed by chemo-mechanical cleaning and filling with a suitable obturating material. The purpose of this case report is to describe a case of unilateral radix entomolaris in primary first molar which is a rare finding.

KEYWORDS

Pediatric Dentistry, Mandibular primary first molar, Radix Entomolaris

INTRODUCTION

A complete and thorough knowledge of primary teeth and their root canal anatomy is very essential for clinical success of the treatment. The presence of dental anomalies is lesser in primary teeth as compared to permanent dentition^{1,6}The overall morphology of primary teeth is completely different as compared to permanent in its enamel, dentin thickness and more accentuated pulp horns which lead to early spread of infection to the pulp as soon as the caries starts.^{1,2} Pediatric endodontics is the method in which infection is removed from the coronal and radicular pulp followed by chemico-mechanical cleaning and obturating with suitable material.^{2,3} Generally mandibular molars (primary or permanent dentition) have two roots that is mesial and distal with three canals and sometimes four canals also which is very rare. Two canals in the mesial root being mesiobuccal and mesiolingual canals and one canal in distal root.^{3,4} A supernumerary root is a developmental anomaly which can affect treatment planning as well as prognosis of any tooth and is known as 'Radix entomolaris' (RE).¹ It is also known as 'extra distolingual root' or a 'distolingual root' or an 'extra third root'.⁷ Root in RE can be a short conical or a mature root of its usual length.⁸ Tratman in 1938 has reported that three rooted mandibular molars are rare with a frequency of <1% in the deciduous dentition and common in the permanent dentition.⁹

Molars are most frequently affected by dental caries at an early age and also they may require a successful endodontic treatment for their long-term retention in the oral cavity. The primary objective of pediatric endodontic therapy is thorough

removal of the pulp tissue from all the roots and canals followed by chemo-mechanical cleaning and filling with a suitable obturating material.¹ Failure to diagnose and treat the supernumerary roots in molars may lead to the failure of endodontic treatment and even premature tooth loss at an early age resulting the patient to suffer functionally, esthetically, and psychologically. Therefore, pediatric dentist must be aware of these unusual root structures to provide the overall benefit to a child patient.¹

CASE REPORT:

A 7-year-old male patient reported to the Department of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry with a chief complain of pain, difficulty while chewing in the lower left back tooth region of the jaw since 1 week. On intraoral clinical examination it was found that deep carious lesions were present in relation to 74 and proximal caries was present with 84 and 85. (Figure-1). Based on the chief complaint and history, RVG of 74 was taken presence of extra root (Radix Entomolaris) was appreciated. (Figure-2) The RVG of 84 and 85 showed presence of 2 roots with no extra root. A provisional diagnosis of chronic irreversible pulpitis was made and endodontic therapy was planned under strict sterilization protocol with 74. Tell-show-do technique of behavior management was done before starting the treatment. After administration of local anesthesia, tooth 74 was isolated under rubber dam. All the carious part was removed and access cavity was made. Three Canals were explored using a size 10 H file and pulp was extirpated with debridement. Working length was taken and after chemo-mechanical cleaning canals were obturated with Metapex followed by stainless steel crown placement. (Figure-3A and 3B) The GIC restoration was done with other active carious lesions in 84 and 85 followed by stainless steel crown.

Figure 1 Showing deep carious lesions were present in relation to 74 and proximal caries was present with 84 and 85

Figure 2 - Preop RVG with 74

Figure 3A and B Postop RVG with 74

Figure 4 - Postop Clinical picture of Mandibular arch

DISCUSSION

The success of pediatric endodontics is determined by a thorough clinical examination, proper diagnosis, competent chemomechanical preparation, and three-dimensional obturation with a suitable obturating material.⁹ The incomplete removal of pulpal tissue and microbes from all the pulp canals is one of the main reasons for the failure of root canal treatment. To avoid this failure a proper radiographic diagnosis play a a very important role in the successful treatment of endodontic therapy in order to rule out any extra canals.¹⁰

Three rooted permanent mandibular first molar and deciduous mandibular second molar have been reported widely in literature, however, the presence of three roots in deciduous mandibular first molar is relatively rare and only a few cases are being reported.¹¹⁻¹³ Various Studies have shown that there is 15.2% of higher incidence rate of Radix entomolaris which is seen in the population of Mongolian origin (Japanese, Malaysian, Chinese, Thai, Eskimo, Aleutian, and American Indian).¹⁴ The radiographs must be taken at different angulations to inorder to decrease the chances of “missed canals”. The prevalence rate of Radix entomolaris is less than 5% in the Indian population and such cases are uncommon during dental treatment. The exact etiology of radix entomolaris is still idiopathic but according to some authors it may be due to disturbance during odontogenesis or may be due to the high degree of genetic penetrance.¹⁵

The etiology of supernumerary roots is unknown, it has been proposed that if during the development of root if the epithelial sheath of Hertwig is folded or disrupted, it can lead to formation of an accessory/supernumerary root canals.

This can be attributed to the most probable cause of the presence of three roots in the present case.¹⁶ According to De Moor et al. the morphology of radix entomolaris canals in the majority of cases, were curved.^{17,18} Winkler and Ahmad in 1997¹⁸, Gupta *et al.*¹⁹ and Ramamurthy *et al.*²⁰ have shown presence of radix entomolaris in primary mandibular molar in the Indian population. Badger et al²¹ reported a case of unilateral three-rooted primary mandibular first molars in a 5-year-old Caucasian boy which was similar to our case.

During endodontic therapy or exodontic procedures, in primary teeth the clinician should be aware of the possibility of an anomalous root. During the extraction procedure clinician should make sure that the crown of the premolar is not trapped in the interradicular area of the primary teeth as during extraction it might cause accidental removal of the developing permanent tooth. The presence of a third root, whether primary or permanent, may have forensic value for identifying people of the Mongoloid race.^{6,21}

CONCLUSION

The presence of radix entomolaris and its complex anatomical morphology creates a challenge for endodontic therapy. The radiograph should be taken at different angulations to look for missed canals . So the accurate radiographic diagnosis and complete knowledge about the variation present in root canal morphology, prevalence and canal configuration of radix entomolaris are the major factors for the success of endodontic treatment.

REFERENCES

1. Kashyap N, Patel S, Rani S, Singh N, Singh CR. Presence of radix entomolaris and paramolaris in primary teeth in children of Garhwa district: A report on two cases. *Indian J Clin Anat Physiol* 2022;9(3):226-228.
2. Radix Entomolaris: Case Report with Clinical Implication *Int. J Clin Pediatr Dent.* 2018;11(6):536–8.
3. Vertucci FJ. Root canal anatomy of the human permanent teeth. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol.* 1984;58(5):589–99.
4. Barker BC, Parsons KC, Mills PR, Williams GL. Anatomy of root canals. III. Permanent mandibular molars. *Aust Dent J.* 1974;19(6):408–13.
5. Calberson FL, DeMoor RJ, Deroose CA. The radix entomolaris and paramolaris: clinical approach in endodontics. *J Endod.* 2007;33(1):58–63.
6. Reena Rani, Sanjay Chachra, Shivangi Verma, Diksha Sharma, Parthvi Singh and Archana Chandel. Unilateral radix entomolaris in primary first molar: A rare entity. *International Journal of Applied Dental Sciences* 2019; 5(3): 297-298
7. De Moor RJ, Deroose CA, Calberson FL. The radix entomolaris in mandibular first molars: an endodontic challenge. *Int Endod J.* 2004; 37:789-99
8. Calberson FL, De Moor RJ, Deroose CA. The radix entomolaris and paramolaris: clinical approach in endodontics. *J Endod.* 2007; 33:58-63
9. Tratman EK. Three rooted lower molars in man and their racial distribution. *Br Dent J.* 1938; 64:264-74.
10. Curzon ME, Curzon JA. Three-rooted mandibular molars in the Keewatin Eskimo. *J Can Dent Assoc (Tor).* 1971;37(2):71–2.

11. Badger GR. Three rooted mandibular first primary molar. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol.* 1982; 53:547
12. Mokhtari S, Mokhtari S. Primary mandibular first molar with three reports. *J Pak Oral Dent J.* 2013; 33:74-5
13. Mayhall JT. Three-rooted deciduous mandibular second molars. *J CanDent Assoc.* 1981; 47:319-21
14. Ferraz J, Pecora J. Three rooted mandibular molars in patients of Mongolian, Caucasian and Negro origin. *Braz Dent J.* 1992; 3:113-7
15. Turner CG. Three-rooted mandibular first permanent molars and the question of American Indian origins. *Am J Phys Anthropol.* 1971;34(2):229–41.
16. Yadav S, Mishra P, Marwah N, Goenka P. Bilateral multirooted first primary molar: A rare case report. *J Indian Acad Oral Med Radiol.* 2017; 29:63-6.
17. DeMoor RJG, Deroose C, Calberson FLG. The radix entomolaris in mandibular first molars: an endodontic challenge. *Int Endod J.* 2004;37(11):789–99.
18. Winkler MP, Ahmad R. Multirooted anomalies in the primary dentition of Native Americans. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 1997; 128:1009-11
19. Gupta S, Nagaveni NB, Chandranee NJ. Three rooted mandibular first primary molar: Report of three cases. *Contemp Clin Dent.* 2012; 3(suppl 1):S134-6
20. Ramamurthy N, Srinivasan I. Bilateral three-rooted primary lower molars. *Indian J Dent Res.* 2012; 23:700
21. Badger GR. Three rooted mandibular first primary molar. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol.* 1982; 53:547